

Evaluation of Cases of Bacteriuria in Pregnant Women and Their Antibigram Attending a Tertiary Care Hospital

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Abstract:

Background: UTI in pregnancy may lead to many complications such as prematurity, low birth weight, death and other adverse foetal sequelae (Gilstrap et al, 2001). It may also cause pyelonephritis and sepsis in mothers. Now a days, many UTI-causing organisms are resistant to different commonly used drugs. Only a few Indian studies have been published on this topic. So, it is reasonable to evaluate pregnant women for UTI during their antenatal checkup in this Institution and give them proper antibiotics to avoid pregnancy complications.

Materials and Methods: This Descriptive Observational Study comprised 246 Antenatal Patients had urine for routine examination and Culture and Sensitivity testing and their Antibigram prepared.

Results: Out of 246 patients, 174 had no growth (70.73%) and 72 (29.27%) had Bacteriuria, mostly Symptomatic - showed maximum sensitivity to Co-trimoxazole Ciprofloxacin, Amikacin, Gentamycin and Cephalosporins.

Conclusions: Periodic urine culture should be performed routinely throughout pregnancy especially during the 1st and 3rd trimester patients. Patients were advised to maintain proper care and hygiene, early detection & treatment. Early detection of UTI and rational use of antibiotics Trimester-wise will help us achieve the best therapeutic advantage for the patients and prevent development of Antibiotic-Resistant Bacterial strains arising from Injudicious use of random antibiotics.

Keywords: Bacteriuria, Asymptomatic, Symptomatic, Gram-negative, Gram-Positive, Culture, Sensitivity, Uro-pathogen.

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Introduction

Urinary tract infections (UTIs) are one of the most common bacterial infections during pregnancy. Although the incidence of bacteriuria in pregnant women is similar to that in their nonpregnant counterparts, the incidence of acute pyelonephritis in pregnant women with bacteriuria is significantly increased, compared with nonpregnant women. [1]

During pregnancy urine becomes less acidic and more likely to contain progesterin's and glucose, both of which boost the potential for bacterial growth. Untreated asymptomatic bacteriuria has been associated with acute pyelonephritis, which may have a role in many maternal and fetal complications. Screening the pregnant women at their antenatal visits, particularly in the second trimester of pregnancy where the bacteriuria is the highest, is a rational approach. [2]

Search for more effective and shorter treatment modalities to increase the patient compliance is relevant at this time. Urine culture is the gold standard screening technique for bacteriuria during

pregnancy. [3] Antibiotic treatment compared to placebo or no treatment is effective in clearing bacteriuria and in reducing the risk of pyelonephritis in pregnancy. [4] The antibacterial agent chosen in pregnancy must be well-tolerated, empirically known to be harmless to the mother and the fetus, and have a low level of bacterial resistance. [5]

Aims and Objectives

- 1) To find out the Prevalence of Urinary Tract Infection among Pregnant women.
- 2) Isolate the types of causative organisms and their relative frequencies.
- 3) To determine their Antibiotic Sensitivity Pattern.

Materials and Methods

Study Design: Institutional based Descriptive Observational Study.

Study Population: Patient who visited the out-patient Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology.

Sample Size: 246cases.

Inclusion Criteria: Pregnant women attending outpatient department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology for their antenatal check-up.

Exclusion Criteria:

- 1) Patient not giving consent.
- 2) Patients having known anomaly of urinary tract
- 3) Sample rejection criteria
 - a) Sample that is not properly collected, or not sent in time or not properly stored
 - b) Sample that has leaked during transport
 - c) Patients already taking antibiotics

Laboratory Investigations, parameters and Procedures: All pregnant patients attending the outdoor within the period from December'22 to May'24 for the antenatal check-up will be advised urine for routine examination and Culture and Sensitivity testing (Nutrient agar, Mac Conkey's agar and Blood agar plates).

Gram Staining from the Growth, Hanging Drop Preparation for Motility Testing, Kirby Bauer Disc Diffusion Method, Biochemical Tests:Catalase Test, Coagulase Test, Indole Production, Urease Test, Citrate Utilization Test, Oxidase Test, Bile Esculin Test, Methyl Red/Voges-Proskauer Tests.

Statistical analysis:

The entire statistical analysis can be carried on 95% confidence interval with 80% power of the test.

The statistical software SPSS version 22 can be used for this type of analysis.

Results

We divided total 246 patients in 3 age groups, i.e. 18-20 years, 21-30 years and 31-40 years. Maximum number of patients, 118 (47.96%) patients belonged to 21-30- years of age group. 18-20 years age group consisted of 106 (43.08%) patients and 22 (8.96%) patients belonged to 31-40 years age group. The prevalence rate is maximum in the patients who belonged to 2nd trimester (26%, 20.75%, 3.67% in 3 age groups).

Table 1: Result of Urine Culture of the patients studied.

Culture colonies	No. of patients	Percentage
No Growth	174	70.73
Colonies < 10 ⁵	5	2.03
Colonies >10 ⁵	67	27.24
Total	246	100

Figure (A). Prevalence rate with respect to age group among the patients who were infected with bacteriuria (n=246)

Table 2: Prevalence of uropathogens (n=67) among the infected patients.

Organism	No. of patients	Percentage
Escherichia coli	28	41.79
Klebsiella spp.	16	23.90
Staphylococcus aureus	09	13.43
Acinetobacter spp.	06	8.95
Proteus spp.	04	5.97

Enterococcus spp.	02	2.98
Pseudomonas aeruginosa	02	2.98

(1). *E. coli* in MacConkey's agar (2). *Proteus spp.* in MacConkey's agar (3). *Staphylococcus aureus* in Nutrient agar (4). *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* in MacConkey's agar

Table 3: Prevalence of pyuria among the patients who were infected with Bacteriuria.

	Age group					
	18 -20 (n=25)		21 – 30 (n=37)		31 -40 (n=05)	
	No. of patients	%	No. of patients	%	No. of patients	%
Bacteriuria without pyuria	05	20	08	21.63	03	60
Bacteriuria with pyuria	20	80	29	78.37	02	40
Total	25	100	37	100	05	100

Table 4: Prevalence of symptomatic and asymptomatic bacteriuria among the patients who were infected.

	Age group					
	18 -20 (n=25)		21 – 30 (n=37)		31 -40 (n=05)	
	No. of patients	%	No. of patients	%	No. of patients	%
Symptomatic Bacteriuria	18	72.00	26	70.27	03	60.00
Asymptomatic Bacteriuria	07	28.00	11	29.73	02	40.00
Total	25	100	37	100	05	100

Table 5: Sensitivity pattern of gram-negative bacteria (n=56)

Anti-microbial agents	Escherichia coli (n=28)			Klebsiella spp. (n=16)			Proteus spp. (n=4)			Acinetobacter spp. (n= 6)			Pseudomonas spp. (n=2)		
	S	I	R	S	I	R	S	I	R	S	I	R	S	I	R
Gentamycin (GEN)	22	2	4	10	2	4	3	1	0	4	0	2	2	0	0
Nitrofurantoin (NIT)	19	2	7	8	1	7	—			3	1	2	1	0	1
Ciprofloxacin (CIP)	23	0	5	13	0	3	2	0	2	3	0	3	2	0	0
Amoxicillin+ Clavulanic (AMC)	16	3	9	9	0	7	1	1	2	—			—		
Imipenem (IPM)	20	1	7	11	1	4	2	1	1	4	1	1	2	0	0
Amikacin (AK)	23	0	5	13	0	3	2	0	2	4	0	2	2	0	0
Co-Trimoxazole (COT)	24	1	3	12	0	4	3	0	1	5	0	1	—		
Ceftazidime (CAZ)	19	0	9	10	2	4	2	0	2	3	0	3	1	0	1
Cefepime (CPM)	21	0	7	11	1	4	3	0	1	4	1	1	1	0	1
Ceftriaxone (CTR)	20	2	6	9	2	5	2	0	2	3	0	3	1	0	1
Piperacillin + Tazobactam(PIT)	21	1	6	11	0	5	1	1	2	5	0	1	0	0	2

Table 6: Sensitivity pattern of gram-positive bacteria (n=11)

Antimicrobial agents	Staphylococcus aureus (n=9)			Enterococcus spp. (n=2)		
	S	I	R	S	I	R
Gentamycin (GEN)	5	1	3			
Nitrofurantoin (NIT)	4	1	4	1	0	1
Ciprofloxacin (CIP)	5	0	4	0	0	2
Teicoplanin (TEI)	6	0	3	2	0	0
Cefoxitin (CX)	7	0	2			
Tetracycline (TE)	5	0	4	1	0	1
Vancomycin (VA)	8	0	1	2	0	0
Meropenem (MRP)	6	1	2	2	0	0

Discussion

Although the prevalence of bacteriuria in pregnant women is similar to those in non-pregnant women, the consequences of infection are much more serious during pregnancy, warranting the prompt diagnosis and treatment of infection. An early detection and treatment of bacteriuria in pregnancy may be of considerable importance not only to forestall acute pyelonephritis and chronic renal failure in the mother, but also to reduce the prematurity & fetal mortality in the offspring. [6] Bacteriuria whether symptomatic or asymptomatic must be treated during the pregnancy in order to prevent complications such as pyelonephritis, premature labor, hypertension, preeclampsia, and septicaemia. [7]

Many studies show advancing age as a risk factor for acquiring ASB in pregnancy because there is decrease in glycogen deposition and reduction in the lactobacillus as a part of ageing process which enhances bacterial adherence and invasion by pathogens and make them more susceptible. [8]

In our study maximum 114(46.34%) patients were having their 1st gravida, 99(40.24%) patients were having their 2nd gravida and 33(13.41%) patients were having their 3rd gravida. Bacteriuria in pregnancy was more common among primigravida (53.85%) compared to multigravida. This association was also not found to be statistically significant ($p = 0.115 > 0.05$). The findings were correlating with the findings of Sudha Kerure et al from Karnataka in 2012. [1]

Maximum no of patients were infected were in 21-30 years age group. And we have found total 27.24% (67) out of 246 patients were suffering from asymptomatic bacteriuria. The ratio was 1:0.027. Maximum no of patients were infected- 21-30 years in age group. And we have found total 27.24% (67) out of 246 patients were suffering from asymptomatic bacteriuria. The ratio was 1:0.027. [9]

Table no 2 showed the uropathogenic findings of the bacteriuria infected patients. 28 (41.79%) patients had *E. coli* and 16 (23.90%) patients had *Klebsiella species*. *Staphylococcus aureus* was found in 9 (13.43%) patients, whereas *Acinetobacter spp.* and *Proteus spp.* infection was found in 6(8.95%) and

4(5.97%) number of patients respectively. *Enterococcus spp.* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* were found in 2(2.98%) patients each. [10]

Prevalence of Gram-negative bacilli were significantly more than the Gram-positive cocci in our study. The most prevalence organism observed in this study was *Escherichia coli* (23.90%). This finding agrees with earlier reports [2] who observed the same predominant trend in *Escherichia coli* infection pattern.

Most of the gram-negative bacilli were highly sensitive to Co-Trimoxazole (81.48%), Amikacin (78.57%) and Ciprofloxacin (76.78%) followed by Gentamicin (73.21%), CPM (71.42%) and Imipenem (69.64%). The isolates were mostly resistant to Nitrofurantoin, Ceftriaxone, Ceftazidime and Amoxiclav having a sensitivity percentage of 59.61%, 62.5%, 62.5% and 54.16% respectively. [11]

The number of ESBL producers were significantly high in number.

The gram-positive organisms showed high sensitivity towards Vancomycin (90.91%). Almost all of the isolated except one were sensitive to vancomycin. Cefoxitin has a sensitivity percentage of 77.78% followed by Teicoplanin and Meropenem both having a sensitivity of 72.73%. The least sensitive drugs were found to be Ciprofloxacin (45.45%), Nitrofurantoin, Tetracycline (54.55%) and Gentamicin (55.56%).

The above-mentioned pattern shows that there is presence of MRSA in a significant number among the isolated cases.

From the sensitivity pattern it was also noted that many of the organisms were multi drug resistant, which is a cause of concern.

Limitations

In spite of every sincere effort my study has lacunae.

The notable short comings of this study are:

1. The sample size was small. Only 246 cases are not sufficient for this kind of study.
2. The study has been done in a single centre.

- The study was carried out in a tertiary care hospital, so hospital bias cannot be ruled out.

Conclusion

Bacteriuria constitutes a big problem due to the increase in prevalence among pregnant women.

Periodic urine culture should be performed routinely throughout pregnancy especially during the 1st and 3rd trimester patients. Patients were advised to maintain proper care and hygiene, early detection & treatment. Searching of risk factors among pregnant women like DM, obstructive UTI/ stones, multiple pregnancy cases showed be taken special care of bacteriuria.

From the above study, it is clearly evident that the emerging resistant pattern of ESBLs now in our college. The Obstetrician must consider the Trimester of pregnancy before starting therapy. There is little direct information about the safety of many newer antibiotics used in UTIs and observational studies or indirect evidences (e.g. Animal Studies) may have numerous confounders. Overall, the safest course is to use the antibiotics those have well-established safety profiles in pregnancy. Therefore, we may conclude that Cephalosporins (e.g. Cefepime, Ceftriaxone, Ceftazidime) can be the the first line of drugs, whereas, Nitrofurantoin (avoided in 1st trimester and between 38-42 weeks), Co-trimoxazole (avoided in 1st trimester and near term), Aminoglycosides (prolonged fetal exposure avoided) and Fluoroquinolones (generally avoided in pregnancy) are to be considered with caution. Early detection of UTI and rational use of antibiotics will help us achieve the best therapeutic advantage for the patients and prevent development of Antibiotic-Resistant Bacterial strains arising from Injudicious use of random antibiotics.

Ethical Approval: Approved by Ethical Communities.

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